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ASTERIX-CAESAR

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Flexible Solar power generation with Compressed Air Energy Storage

4

Years

Oct 23 - Sept 27

7.2

M€ Budget

17

Partners

10

Countries

6-7

TRL

Main Impacts

Higher share of variable output renewables

Higher efficiency of CSP plants

Reduced operation and maintenance costs of CSP plants

Achieving EU targets for Global Leadership in CSP

CENER

NATIONAL RENEWABLE ENERGY CENTRE

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